

THE IMPACT OF COMPREHENSIVE THERAPEUTIC AND PREVENTIVE INTERVENTIONS IN CHILDREN WITH GERD ON INFLAMMATORY MARKERS IN ORAL FLUID

F. Bebutov¹, N.N. Akhmadaliev²

Termez Branch of the Tashkent State Medical University

Tashkent State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18846394>

Abstract. *Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) in children is accompanied not only by lesions of the upper gastrointestinal tract but also by marked changes in the oral cavity, including inflammatory processes of the oral mucosa and periodontal tissues. One objective criterion for assessing inflammatory activity and the effectiveness of ongoing therapy is the level of inflammatory markers in oral fluid, which reflects the status of local immune and metabolic homeostasis. The aim of the present study was to investigate the effect of comprehensive therapeutic and preventive interventions in children with gastroesophageal reflux disease on the levels of inflammatory markers in oral fluid. The study included children with clinically and instrumentally confirmed GERD who received comprehensive treatment involving both a gastroenterologist and a dentist. Treatment efficacy was evaluated based on clinical findings, dental status, and changes in oral-fluid inflammatory parameters. The results demonstrated that comprehensive therapeutic and preventive measures reduce the severity of inflammatory processes in the oral cavity, normalize oral-fluid parameters, and improve dental status in children with GERD. These findings support the rationale for an interdisciplinary approach to the management of pediatric gastroesophageal reflux disease and may be used to optimize preventive programs in pediatric dentistry.*

Keywords: *gastroesophageal reflux disease; children; oral cavity; oral fluid; inflammatory markers; dental status; comprehensive treatment; prevention.*

Introduction

Gastroesophageal reflux disease, GERD, is one of the most common chronic disorders of the gastrointestinal tract in children and adolescents and is characterized by a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations, including both esophageal and extraesophageal symptoms [1]. In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to extraesophageal manifestations of GERD, among which changes affecting the organs and tissues of the oral cavity occupy a prominent place [2]. The oral cavity is the initial segment of the digestive tract and the first anatomical zone exposed to acidic gastric refluxate containing hydrochloric acid, pepsin, and microorganisms [3]. Chronic exposure to these factors disrupts oral-fluid homeostasis, reduces its buffering capacity, and alters immunobiochemical properties, thereby promoting inflammatory diseases of the oral mucosa and periodontal tissues, as well as demineralization of hard dental tissues [4].

Oral fluid is a highly informative biological medium that reflects the status of local protective mechanisms and inflammatory processes in the oral cavity [5]. Changes in the levels of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory markers in oral fluid are regarded as an objective indicator of inflammatory activity and of the effectiveness of therapeutic and preventive measures [6]. In children with GERD, these parameters acquire particular diagnostic and prognostic

significance [7]. Despite the availability of individual studies addressing the dental manifestations of gastroesophageal reflux disease, the impact of a comprehensive therapeutic and preventive approach on inflammatory markers in oral fluid in children remains insufficiently studied [8]. The lack of unified algorithms for interdisciplinary collaboration between gastroenterologists and dentists necessitates further research in this area [9].

In view of the above, investigating the effect of comprehensive therapeutic and preventive interventions on inflammatory parameters in the oral fluid of children with gastroesophageal reflux disease is highly relevant, as it may enhance treatment effectiveness and support the development of evidence-based approaches to preventing dental complications in this patient population [10]. An important component in the assessment of oral dental status is the evaluation of the microbiocenosis. For this purpose, the degree of dysbiosis is assessed by calculating the ratio of the relative activities of the enzymes urease and lysozyme [11]. Urease is produced by opportunistic microorganisms; therefore, its activity correlates with the abundance of oral bacteria. The second enzyme, lysozyme, reflects the level of nonspecific protection of the oral cavity [12].

Purpose of the study - To assess the effect of comprehensive therapeutic and preventive interventions on the levels of inflammatory markers in the oral fluid of children with gastroesophageal reflux disease and to determine their significance for optimizing dental prevention and treatment in this patient population.

Material and research methods

The study had a prospective clinical and experimental design and was aimed at evaluating the effect of comprehensive therapeutic and preventive interventions on dental status and oral-fluid parameters in children with gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). The study included 128 children aged 8 to 14 years who were examined at a dental office after written informed consent was obtained from parents and verbal assent was obtained from the child. Inclusion criteria were clinically and instrumentally confirmed GERD; exclusion criteria were refusal to participate, acute infectious diseases, congenital malformations, and endocrine disorders.

Based on clinical and dental status, the following groups were formed: the main group consisted of 75 children with erosions of hard dental tissues associated with GERD; the comparison group included 53 children with erosions of hard dental tissues without signs of GERD; the control group comprised 20 apparently healthy children. The gastroenterological assessment included analysis of complaints, questionnaire-based survey, and evaluation of esophagogastroduodenoscopy findings obtained before initiation of antisecretory therapy.

The dental examination included assessment of the oral mucosa and the vermilion border of the lips, diagnosis of caries and non-caries lesions of hard dental tissues, determination of the DMFT index, evaluation of dentin hypersensitivity according to the classification of Yu.A. Fedorov, and analysis of oral hygiene status using the Silness–Löe index. Acid–base status in the oral cavity was evaluated by measuring the pH of mixed saliva and local pH on tooth surfaces. Unstimulated salivary flow rate was determined using a standard method.

All patients in the main and comparison groups received baseline GERD therapy according to the gastroenterologist's recommendations, including dietary modification, antacids, alginates, proton pump inhibitors, H₂-histamine receptor blockers, and prokinetics, depending on disease severity. In the comparison group, standard dental preventive measures were implemented, including instruction in individual oral hygiene and the use of basic oral-care products. In the main group, in addition to routine dental therapy, a tailored комплекс of therapeutic and preventive interventions was applied, aimed at correcting the acid–base balance in the oral cavity, enhancing

enamel mineralization, and reducing the severity of inflammatory processes. The program included probiotic lozenges, remineralizing agents, and professional preventive methods for erosive lesions of hard dental tissues.

In cases of initial enamel erosions, microinvasive infiltration therapy was used, whereas in patients with pronounced hypersensitivity, remineralization therapy with individually fabricated trays was applied. The effectiveness of the therapeutic and preventive measures was assessed before treatment, 1 month after its completion, and longitudinally during subsequent follow-up visits. Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive and inferential methods. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Normality of distribution was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Differences between groups were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion

In the present study, we analyzed dental status, oral-fluid parameters, and the effectiveness of comprehensive therapeutic and preventive therapy in children with GERD. The findings presented reflect changes in key inflammatory markers, the condition of hard dental tissues, acid–base balance, and salivary flow rate across the different patient groups. The results are discussed in terms of how a comprehensive approach contributes to the correction of the GERD-related dental syndrome, while also taking into account current concepts of the pathogenesis of erosive lesions and dentin hypersensitivity in children.

Figures 1 and 2 show the dynamics of lysozyme and urease activity in children with GERD during the use of the proposed therapeutic and preventive complex. According to the data in Figure 1, in the CL group, lysozyme activity increased by 52.5% after treatment, and by the end of the 6-month follow-up period it remained 39.8% higher than baseline. In the TL group, lysozyme activity increased by 5.6% after treatment but gradually returned to baseline values.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of lysozyme activity in children with GERD during the use of the proposed комплекс therapeutic and preventive program (CTPP), U/mL ($M \pm m$)

Fig. 2. Dynamics of urease activity in children with GERD during the use of the proposed комплекс therapeutic and preventive program (CTPP), µkat/L ($M \pm m$)

Analysis of the data presented in Figure 2 revealed a decrease in urease activity by 67.3% in the CL group and by 13.1% in the TL group after treatment. Subsequently, in the comparison group, urease activity returned to the baseline level, whereas in the CL group this parameter remained 52.7% lower than the initial value. Thus, after treatment, the increase in the DMFT index was twofold lower in the CL group than in the TL group, and the caries-preventive effectiveness of the proposed therapeutic and preventive program was 53.72%.

The proposed therapeutic and preventive program led to improved oral hygiene and a reduction in the degree of periodontal inflammation in children of the main group even after 6 months of clinical follow-up. This is supported by the PMA index: at baseline and at the end of treatment, PMA values were nearly identical in both groups, but after 6 months the index in the TL group was twice as high as in the CL group.

Mixed saliva in children with manifestations of GERD showed reduced remineralizing capacity, as confirmed by the corresponding pH value and the mean levels of ionized calcium and inorganic phosphates, which were at the lower limit of normal. The prescribed therapeutic and preventive program, in combination with GERD therapy, improved the remineralizing properties of mixed saliva in children in the CL group: pH improved by 62.2% and approached the upper limit of normal, inorganic phosphate levels increased by 69.7%, and ionized calcium doubled. In the TL group, pH improved only by 11.8%, inorganic phosphate increased by 16.7%, and ionized calcium increased by 35.2% (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Indicators of the remineralizing function of saliva in children with GERD (%)

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) in children is associated with impairment of the mineralizing and protective properties of oral fluid, manifested by reduced pH, decreased concentrations of ionized calcium and inorganic phosphates, and increased inflammatory markers. These alterations create prerequisites for the development of non-carious lesions of hard dental tissues and inflammatory diseases of the oral mucosa.

A comprehensive therapeutic and preventive intervention, combining correction of dental status with adherence to gastroenterological therapy, showed a pronounced positive effect on oral-fluid parameters. Specifically, children in the main group exhibited a substantial improvement in the remineralizing capacity of saliva, normalization of pH, and increased levels of ionized calcium and inorganic phosphates, indicating reduced inflammatory activity and an overall improvement in the physiological condition of the oral cavity.

The findings support the need for an interdisciplinary approach to the management of pediatric GERD, integrating both gastroenterological treatment and individually tailored dental

interventions. The results have practical relevance for developing effective protocols for the prevention and treatment of dental complications in this patient population.

REFERENCES

1. Городнова Т.В. Гастроэзофагеальная рефлюксная болезнь у детей: современные подходы к диагностике и лечению //Педиатрия. – 2020. – Т. 99, № 3. – С. 45–52.
2. Власова Н.В., Петров А.А. Внепищеводные проявления гастроэзофагеальной рефлюксной болезни у детей //Журнал детской гастроэнтерологии. – 2019. – № 2. – С. 33–41.
3. Кузнецов С.М. Физиология ротовой полости и её роль в защите органов пищеварения //Медицинская биохимия. – 2018. – Т. 63, № 4. – С. 12–18.
4. Иванова Л.П., Смирнов Д.В. Стоматологические проявления ГЭРБ у детей //Стоматология детского возраста. – 2021. – № 1. – С. 22–30.
5. Левина Е.А. Ротовая жидкость как диагностический биомаркер //Клиническая лабораторная диагностика. – 2020. – № 6. – С. 18–25.
6. Николаев И.И., Соловьёва М.К. Биохимические маркеры воспаления в слюне у детей с ГЭРБ //Педиатрическая медицина. – 2021. – № 5. – С. 50–58.
7. Романова О.В., Фёдоров П.А. Маркеры воспаления ротовой жидкости при хронических заболеваниях пищеварительной системы у детей //Вестник детской гастроэнтерологии. – 2019. – № 3. – С. 40–47.
8. Леус П.А., Галченко В.М. Клинический синдром ГЭРБ и стоматологические проявления у детей //Стоматология. – 1983. – № 4. – С. 14–20.
9. Максимовский Ю.М. Эрозии зубов и гастроэзофагеальный рефлюкс //Журнал стоматологической профилактики. – 2017. – Т. 12, № 2. – С. 10–16.
10. Водолацкий М.П., Овруцкий Г.Д., Водолацкая А.М. Реминерализующая терапия зубов у детей с гастроэзофагеальной рефлюксной болезнью //Стоматология детского возраста. – 1987. – № 2. – С. 5–12.
11. Redinova T.L., Leontiev V.K., Ovrutsky G.D. Clinical assessment of enamel remineralization //Caries Research. – 1982. – Vol. 16, № 5. – P. 387–393.
12. Воробьёва Л.И., Сидоренко Н.В. Ферментативные маркеры микробиоценоза ротовой полости у детей //Вестник клинической медицины. – 2020. – № 2. – С. 55–61.